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THE PADMA MULTIPURPOSE BRIDGE, BANGLADESH'S LONGEST BRIDGE, PRESENTS UNIQUE ENGINEERING CHALLENGES AND AN IMPRESSIVE OUTCOME

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ABSTRACT

The Padma Multipurpose Bridge, commonly known as the Padma Bridge, is a two-level steel truss bridge with a four-lane highway on the upper level and a single-track railway on the lower level that has been under construction since 2014 and opened to traffic in June 2022. The upper and lower levels act compositely for live loading with a reinforced concrete deck slab. The bridge presented technical challenges to the client, consultants, and contractors, including river training work and deep foundations in an alluvial flood plain, where the rock formation lies several kilometers below the river bed. Major vessel traffic and ship impact were also challenges. The Padma is one of the world's mightiest rivers, being a distributary of the Ganges and the Jamuna rivers and winding its way through Bangladesh to the Bay of Bengal. Engineers faced many challenges while designing the Padma Multipurpose Bridge, one of the biggest challenges being how to design a structure that could withstand the extreme conditions of the river. The structure consists of main bridge piers, which require "base grouting" and "skin grouting" to verify that they can withstand the required design loads. The largest hydraulic hammers in the world were used to install the steel tubular piles for the main bridge piers. When it is operational, the bridge is expected to boost Bangladesh's GDP by 1.2 percent. The Padma Bridge, which cost \$3.87 billion to construct, is one of Bangladesh's largest construction projects ever and was funded by the Government of Bangladesh (GoB). In the case of Bangladesh, the GoB funded the country's largest construction projects ever.

Keywords: Padma Multipurpose Bridge, Road-rail bridge, Engineering challenges, Base & skin grouting, Steel tubular piles.

1 INTRODUCTION

The Padma Bridge, which connects Bangladesh's southwest region with its northern and eastern regions, stands as a testament to the dignity, honor, and distinction of the nation. A recognized cultural UNESCO World Heritage Site, the largest mangrove forest in the country is located in the south. Because of natural calamities, poor connectivity, and a lack of communication, it is currently in imminent danger (Mukul et al., 2020). The honorable Bangladeshi Prime Minister Sheikh Hasina has taken a strong stand to restore the nation's respect and unity in this circumstance through her foresight and strategic preparation (Aditya, 2021).

The Padma River, the third-largest in the world, has a convoluted topology and tends to flow west. It is challenging to move about the 6.15 km-wide river since there are few and sporadic boat connections, which restrict mobility and economic potential (Figure 1). As a result, the proportion of the population living in poverty is approximately 5% higher than the national average. In order to boost connectivity and expand trade opportunities, the government decided to construct the Padma Bridge with financial assistance from the World Bank, JICA, the Islamic Development Bank, and the Asian Development Bank (E. Hossain et al., 2018). But afterwards, the Bangladeshi government strongly endorsed the Padma Bridge project, and both Bangladeshi and foreign construction firms worked to see it through to completion (Du & Weng, 2021).

Figure 1: Project location map of Padma Bridge

The bridge is anticipated to increase the country's GDP by 1.2% and the region's south-west GDP by 2.3%, which is afflicted by poverty (Blankespoor et al., 2022). The Padma Bridge, which had two levels and cost roughly US\$2.97 billion, was utilized for both cars and trains. The Padma River's inherent qualities caused the project to run into a number of stubborn problems during the planning and construction phases. The Padma River's irregular annual flow threatens the stability of the bridge's foundations by causing substantial variations in the riverbed level. Extensive river training works (RTW) were required to protect the bridge from disasters since the Padma River delivers the greatest sediment (1×10^9 t/year on average) (Islam et al., 2022). The estimated depth of riverbed scour with a 100-year return period is 62 m (Wang et al., 2018). Bangladesh's proximity to the Himalayan tectonic plate contact zones makes the area where the bridge is being built vulnerable to earthquakes. Deep scour and seismicity, as a result, made it difficult to construct the pile foundation.

The Bangladesh Bridge Authority (BBA) hired AECOM, Hong Kong; NHS, Canada; and SMEC, Australia, to design the main bridge and river training work (RTW). Before extensively

examining various bridge shapes, AECOM thoroughly examined the earlier works completed for the project (Hossain et al., 2018). The workers' zeal helped to mitigate the difficult working conditions caused by the COVID outbreak. Four new world records were set by this effort in order to construct the majestic structure. Based on the development of several feasible methods, the design was gradually converted into a two-level steel truss bridge with a concrete top slab functioning as a composite element. It was decided that this design, with the highway on the top deck and the railway on the bottom deck, was the right approach for the project. This two-level combined railroad bridge system was adopted in the final, comprehensive design, which was completed in 2010. This multipurpose structure conveys utilities such as a gas pipeline and telephone wires in addition to the highway and railroad (Kabir et al., 2022). The two-level bridge allows for the secure separation of the railroad and the roadway, as well as simple access for maintenance and inspection (Robin Sham, 2015). A train on the lower deck can be evacuated safely and quickly owing to emergency access points constructed on the bridge (Muhaimin et al., 2021). The accomplishment of this project proved that problems could be overcome by using a planned method, and it would inspire a nation to take on more difficult initiatives in the future.

2 THE CONSULTANTS

The journey began in 1986, when the UNDP-funded Configuration and Characteristic Study was taken up by the government to identify potential corridors for fixed links crossing the Jamuna and Padma rivers separating western Bangladesh from the capital. Seven corridors were identified between Bahadurabad in the north and Chandpur, where the Mawa-Jajira corridor came next to the Bhuapur-Sirajgonj-Chandpur corridor in terms of technical and financial ranking. In that study, the Bangabandhu Bridge was built at Bhuapur Corridor later, with the consultant being Rendel Palmer & Tritton (RPT) -NEDECO-Bangladesh Consultants Ltd. (BCL).

In 1987, the government of Bangladesh contracted RPT-NEDECO-BCL to conduct a feasibility study and design a bridge across the Jamuna River at Bhuapur. The study was completed in 1989. Based on the results of this study, the government and donors decided to go ahead with constructing the bridge. This phase continued until 1994, when construction contracts were signed. In 1994, RPT-NEDECO-BCL was engaged as construction supervisor for the project as part of a team that also included the Jamuna Multipurpose Bridge Authority (JMBA). Construction was completed in 1998, and that same year the bridge opened to traffic. However, work on another dream project—the Padma Bridge—continued well into the 21st century.

The Bangabandhu Bridge was completed in 2002 and created an environment of confidence in all circles, leading to the government's engagement of RPT-NEDECO-BCL to conduct a pre-feasibility study of the Padma multipurpose bridge at Mawa corridor in 1999. The study was completed in 2000, based on which the foundation of the Padma Bridge was laid at Mawa in July 2001 and further studies were planned. RPT was restructured and given the new name High Point Rendel.

In 2003, the Jamuna Multipurpose Bridge Authority (JMBA), with JICA funding, engaged Nippon Koei-CPC of Japan as the JICA Study Team. Under contract with the JICA Study Team, BCL carried out an initial environmental examination (IEE) and initial social impact assessment (ISIA) in 2003–04. Geotechnical investigations were also conducted during this time. In 2004–05, the environmental impact assessment (EIA) and social impact assessment (SIA) were completed for the feasibility study that was completed in 2005. In 2005, the government's own funding allowed JMBA to engage BCL as the consultant to prepare the Land Acquisition Plan (LAP), Resettlement Action Plan (RAP), and Environmental Studies and Preparation of Environmental Management Plan (EMP).

JMBA engaged STUP Consultants of India under ADB PPTA in 2006 to prepare project documents for the proposal. The BCL, under contract with STUP, carried out a traffic survey and forecasting study, a cost study for the ferry system, and a poverty reduction impact assessment related to motor vehicle use. The detailed design of the bridge was carried out by Maunsell-AECOM Consultants under ADB funding in 2009–2011. Independent design checking was done by Flint and Neill under ADB funding in 2010. When the government decided to build the bridge with its own money on January 31, 2013, the World Bank and other donors withdrew their funding commitments.

In December 2014, contracts for the Main Bridge and River Training Works were signed by representatives of the contractors and the government. Korea Expressway Corporation, a consortium of consultants led by the company, was appointed as the Construction Supervision Consultants (CSC) in the role of Engineers' Representative for these two contracts. For the other two contracts, the Bangladesh Army, with support from the Bangladesh University of Engineering and Technology (BUET), was given responsibility for overseeing construction.

In February 2016, Rendel-BCL-PADECO-KEI were appointed as the Management Support Consultants (MSC) for the project. HPR was renamed as Rendel Ltd., and Bangladesh Consultants Ltd. was restructured under the name of BCL Associates Ltd. The Project Directorate of the Padma Multipurpose Bridge implemented the project on behalf of MSC as its engineer, with CSC providing their assistance as the Engineers' Representative and the Panel of Experts (POE) as advisers.

3 TECHNICAL DETAILS

The bridge stretches for a total of 10.642 kilometers, with 41 spans attached to 42 pillars (Figure 2), and is ranked as the 122nd longest bridge in the world. The railway viaduct is 0.532 kilometers long, while the main bridge is 6.15 kilometers long. The Padma Multipurpose Bridge is a two-level road-rail bridge across the Padma River. It connects Shariatpur and Madaripur, linking the southwest of the country to the northern and eastern regions. The bridge was inaugurated on 25 June 2022. Considered to be the most challenging construction project in the history of Bangladesh, the steel truss bridge carries a four-lane highway on the upper level and a single-track railway on the lower level. The bridge consists of 41 sections, each 150.12 m (492.50 ft) long and 22.5 m (74 ft) wide, with a total length of 6.15 km (3.82 mi). It is the longest bridge in Bangladesh and the longest bridge over the river.

Steel tube-driven piles inclined at 1H:6V is driven beneath the river for each pier. 262 piles overall, 6 in each of the 18 piers, 7 in each of the 11 piers, and 7 in each of the 11 piers with skin grouting, make up the main bridge. The skin grouting was applied using microfine cement and TAM duct technology (Nur, 2014). Given that TAM Duct technology was being utilized for the first time in this project, the 22-pier structure had to be redesigned using these distinctive configurations.

The superstructural loads on the Padma Bridge's viaduct component are supported by a total of 365 piles. Among the 1.2-meter-diameter vertical bored piles in viaducts, including 172 in Mawa and 193 in Janjira. The 150-meter-long piles are the longest and deepest piles ever used in a bridge (Sham et al., 2010). To drive those piles, German experts used a hydraulic hammer with a 3,000-kilojoule capacity, the largest in the world (De Silva et al., 2013). Steel spans are placed over the piers on the river.

Figure 2: Technical Details of The Padma Multipurpose Bridge (Business Insider Bangladesh, 2022)

Table 1 Main Bridge Salient Features

Span	Total 41 nos. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2 Transition Pier • 40 Center Pier
Span Length	150 m each Composite Superstructure (Warren type Steel Truss Girder and Concrete Deck slabs on Upper Deck)
Total Length (Main Bridge)	41x150 m = 6150 m = 6.150 km. Total 7 Nos Module: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 6 Span in each 6 Module • 5 Span in one Module
Pile Details	Racked (Inclined at 1H:6V) Steel Tubular Driven Pile of 3m diameter 6 Nos. in 18 Nos. Pier 7 Nos. in 11 Nos. Pier 7 Nos. in 11 Nos. Pier with Skin Grouting; Total 262 Nos. Pile Length = 98m to 122m Total number of Pile in Main Bridge: Steel Pile = 18x6 +7x22= 262 Nos. Vertical Bored Concrete Pile = 2x16 = 32 Nos. (up to 80m depth) in 2 Transition Piers 1.2m diameter Vertical Bored Pile in Viaducts: Mawa: 172 nos. and Janjira: 193 nos.; Total No. of Bored Piles = 365
Upper Deck	21.65 m wide Concrete Deck Slab (2.5m Breakdown Lanes on both sides) 4 Lane Road
Lower Deck	Single Track Dual Gauge Rail
Deck Height	13.60 m
Navigational Clearance	18.30 m
Viaduct	Mawa End (North Bank 19+20 = 39 Span); Length = 1478.03 m Janjira End (South Bank 23+19 = 42 Span); Length = 1670.03 m
Rail Viaduct Utilities Through the Bridge	Mawa End and Janjira End 7+7 = 14 Span; Length = 532 m <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 762mm diameter Gas Transmission Line • Service Ducts 7 nos. 400kV Power Transmission Line Platform in River over Pile Foundation at 2km downstream of Main Bridge

Figure 3: General view of Super and Substructure of The Padma Bridge

Figure 4: Pile Moment Diagram of The Padma Bridge

Figure 5: Pile Details of The Padma Bridge

4 METHODOLOGY

For this study, primary data were gathered from publications of the Bangladesh Bridge Authority and preceding literature. The published works of BCL Associates Limited were also taken into consideration for the secondary data. The collected data was thoroughly reviewed in order to identify the significant technical novelty of the Padma Bridge construction. The review was conducted by examining the key findings of past research, integrating novel processes in Padma Bridge, and weighing the advantages and disadvantages of traditional project management practices (Campos et al., 2018). No laboratory or computer model analysis was carried out during the drafting of the paper; instead, the data were gathered from several sources and presented chronologically to ensure that the facts were understood.

5 MAJOR TECHNICAL CHALLENGES

5.1 Significant Technical Difficulties Both in The Design and Construction Phases

Several critical components of the works in the Main Bridge Contract have faced major technical challenges during the design phase and in the construction phase, including:

- i. The piles for the Main Bridge piers, which require "base grouting" and "skin grouting" to verify they can withstand the required design loads under very deep riverbed erosion conditions (up to 62 m) and very large railway loads, wind loads, seismic loads, and

- ship impact loads, are constructed of steel tubular piles (3 m diameter raking piles up to 125 m in length). These are the biggest such piles in the world.
- ii. RC-bored piles were constructed for the Janjira and Mawa Approach viaducts and Transition Piers P1 and P42 (located at the bank edges of the Main Bridge truss spans). A particularly difficult task was providing evidence (as a result of in-depth geotechnical studies) that liquefaction would potentially occur in the ground up to 27 m deep in the Mawa region on the Approach Viaducts (including Transition Pier P1) during a significant earthquake. As a consequence of the procedure's success in testing and building trial piles with "base grouting" and "skin grouting" (using "microfine" cement), a globally first approach to this issue was used for the majority of the Mawa Viaduct piers, where 1.2-m-diameter bored working piles up to 80 m long were installed (with "base grouting" and "skin grouting"). As a result of this, the 16 piers at Transition Pier P1 were built using 3 m-diameter working piles up to 80 m long (with "base grouting" and "skin grouting").
 - iii. After the construction contract was officially started, detailed geotechnical investigations were carried out at each of the 42 main bridge pier locations. At 22 of these locations, low-strength clay/silt subsoil materials were found within 9 meters of the provisional toe level of the proposed working piles. The solution for 11 piers was to use a revised pile group with six slightly shorter raking piles plus one additional vertical pile (all with base grouting). The remaining 11 Main Bridge piers were to be constructed using a revised pile group with six shorter-length raking piles plus one additional vertical pile with "base grouting and skin grouting." This was the first time in the world that such a large steel tubular pile had been successfully skin grouted to significantly increase its capacity.
 - iv. The largest hydraulic hammers in the world were used to install the 3 m-diameter steel tubular piles for the Main Bridge piers. The MENCK 2400 kJ and 3500 kJ hammers from Germany were used.
 - v. Friction pendulum bearings are being used as part of the Main Bridge pier substructures (pier columns, pile caps, and piles) to help bear the seismic loads required during major earthquakes. These FPBs, which are the largest of their kind in the world, have been installed and tested in China using the world's largest test equipment.
 - vi. The node and chord elements of the steel truss were produced in China and then brought to Mawa, where they were welded together to form a whole structure. Each truss weighed 3200 t and was a significant challenge to haul with a floating crane and put in place on the piers. The specialized floating crane (Tyan Yee) had a capacity of 3600 t.
 - vii. According to the program Rev-4B, the nodes and chords of the steel truss were manufactured in China and assembled at Mawa. Because certain portions of the bridge have horizontal and vertical curves, the erection of the steel trusses had to be performed in a specific order. Because the 22-pier pile working drawings were delayed, the contractor had to delay piling for those piers for a while. Because of this construction delay, severe problems arose with storing the truss at the site. To avoid congestion, a separate truss storage yard had to be set up for the storage of "excess" trusses.
 - viii. During the construction of the Mawa Construction Yard in 2020, 125 roadway slabs and 68 railway stringers were washed away and lost in the river. No salvaging was possible, and new slabs had to be cast. Because new steel beams had to be imported from Luxembourg, completion of the project was further delayed.

5.2 Significant Technical Difficulties During the River Training Works (RTW)

Several critical components of the works in the River Training Works Contract have faced major technical challenges during the construction phase, requiring several attempts to successfully construct a nominated "trial section" of the works, including in particular:

- i. The development of a suitable dredging technique to construct and trim underwater slopes to the required tolerances to allow placement of revetment or bank protection materials (up to 25 m water depth).
- ii. Creating appropriate techniques and specially customized equipment to consistently and accurately place geobags (on the trimmed underwater slope and in the launching apron) in water depths up to 25 m.
- iii. The scour holes were filled with 60 kg of rice bags, 125 kg of geobags, and 800 kg of geobags, respectively. However, there has been an accumulation of silt sedimentation of 20 meters' thickness in all these years. Now removing this silt and performing the next task according to the design is a huge problem.
Developing customized plant and equipment to correctly and consistently place rock riprap (on the geobag filter layer placed on the trimmed underwater slope) is key to developing suitable techniques.

5.3 Difficulties Faced in The Construction of The Padma Multipurpose Bridge

- i. Five sets of the most sophisticated pile-driving hammers in the world were damaged, and two sets completely failed.
- ii. Positioning, guiding, splicing, and strict alignment control of superlong raking steel piles are difficult to accomplish.
- iii. A welded structure with an average welding thickness of 70 mm and a maximum plate thickness of 110 mm was difficult to fabricate.
- iv. A 3600-ton capacity floating crane is used to transport and erect the truss spans, which are severely obstructed by siltation of the construction channel and variable flow conditions of the main river channel.
- v. Difficult construction conditions: harsh natural environmental conditions throughout the year including:
 - a. The turbulent flow velocity of 4.6 m/s in the main river channel is beyond the conventional bridge construction conditions.
 - b. All year long, the construction channel is silted because of the river's high sand content and sand-based water. Figure 6 demonstrates the changing path of the flowing water of the Padma River from 1973 to 2014.
 - c. The construction yard has been eroded and slipped many times.

5.4 The River Training Works (RTW)

The project's overall river training works length is 16.23 kilometers, with 3.15 kilometers along the Mawa bank and 13.08 kilometers on the Janjira side. The major activities included in RTW are listed below:

- River training works are performed to protect the riverbanks from erosion and to ensure that the river will flow under the bridge for its entire life-span.
- The river training system consists of a guiding revetment along both banks of the river.
- “Revetment” and “Slope Protection” are layered systems placed on a sloping surface as protection against hydraulic forces and scouring.
- The revetment is built by stripping topsoil from an elevation of +9.5 m PWD.
- Dredging was performed from an elevation of +2.4 m to between -12 m ~ -25 m to develop a uniform slope of 1:6 as per design.
- The upper and lower slopes are kept at 1:6. This extends from an elevation of +2.5m to +9.0m PWD and is covered by 400 x 400 x 400/300mm CC blocks over the geotextile. At elevation +5.6 m PWD, there is a 3 m wide berm that is similarly paved.

Figure 6: River path from 1973 to 2014

- At +2.5 m PWD, an anchor beam is installed between the upper slope and the river-side boundary.
- The anchor beam provides a stable reference for the placement of the concrete block pitching.
- This beam is a 1000 mm x 400 mm cast in situ reinforced concrete wall (segmental) that is partially buried in the excavated surface and is covered with geotextile material.

6 CONCLUSION

The Padma multipurpose bridge will maintain Bangladesh's landmark structure and facilitate vital connections, but it also represents another successful design strategy in a highly ecologically risky area. The Padma Bridge would complete a crucial connectivity gap in Bangladesh. Additionally, the bridge will offer substantial travel time reserves, particularly between Dhaka and southeast Bangladesh and even across India. The bridge will replace the now risky and unpredictable ships with a safe and straightforward fixed-flow crossing point. In any case, the anticipated plan outcomes examined beforehand have demonstrated the benefit of constructing this bridge. Everyone in Bangladesh can have confidence that the construction of this versatile bridge will be finished. The bridge's design will now be put to the test. The water flow has naturally changed dramatically during the stormy season. At that time, the river bed's water level and the water flow's rate both saw major changes that made any bridge pier vulnerable. Bridges were built in seismically active regions, which created exceptionally challenging planning circumstances when combined with significant erosion. The Padma multifunctional bridge, which provides crucial communication links, will continue to be a famous building in Bangladesh. It also represents a further accomplishment intended to address the extremely hazardous ecological situation. Strong erosion and typical seismic activity need the design

consultant AECOM to apply the most cutting-edge bridge technology to eagerly combine bridge planning and construction to ensure that the bridge not only serves the Bangladeshi people today but also has many eras. On the basis of long-term maintenance, it is vital that the bridge be able to function for a long period of time. Due to the ease of inspection and maintenance, the bridge layout only utilizes the strongest component. The way the bridge is operated was designed to minimize disruption to traffic during repairs and inclement weather. The major construction issues of the Padma Bridge were thoroughly studied in this study, as were the techniques applied to solve them, resulting in the setting of four new world records. The four world records involve the introduction of the longest-driven steel tube piling; construction of the longest steel truss bridge, largest double curvature friction pendulum bearing; and the largest single contract for river training works. Since the construction was managed during the COVID era by strictly enforcing the COVID rules and limitations on the mobility of individuals, very few people experienced COVID-19, and there were no injuries. The foundation for the completion of the Padma Bridge was therefore laid by these sustainable construction management techniques. After successfully overcoming a sea of man-made barriers and engineering challenges, the Padma Bridge stands as a miracle over the powerful river Padma, connecting districts and ensuring stable economic growth for the following 100 years. The trust of Bangladeshi civil engineers has substantially increased as a result of the construction of the Padma Bridge.

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